

MIRREM

Measuring Irregular Migration

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MirreM Spring School Syllabus and Suggested Readings

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THE MIRREM PROJECT

MirreM examines estimates and statistical indicators on the irregular migrant population in Europe as well as related policies, including the regularisation of migrants in irregular situations.

MirreM analyses policies defining migrant irregularity, stakeholders' data needs and usage, and assesses existing estimates and statistical indicators on irregular migration in the countries under study and at the EU level. Using several coordinated pilots, the project develops new and innovative methods for measuring irregular migration and explores if and how these instruments can be applied in other socio-economic or institutional contexts. Based on a broad mapping of regularisation practices in the EU as well as detailed case studies, MirreM will develop 'regularisation scenarios' to better understand conditions under which regularisation should be considered as a policy option. Together with expert groups that will be set up on irregular migration data and regularisation, respectively, the project will synthesise findings into a Handbook on data on irregular migration and a Handbook on pathways out of irregularity. The project's research covers 20 countries, including 12 EU countries and the United Kingdom.

More information on the project is available at www.irregularmigration.eu.

TO CITE

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KEYWORDS

Training material; Syllabus; Irregular migration data; Statistical Indicators; Estimation Methods; Ethics

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INTRODUCTION

From March 19 to 21, 2025, the University for Continuing Education (Danube University) Krems hosted the MirreM Spring School, an intensive training programme designed for researchers and professionals working on irregular migration, following the IMISCOE Spring Conference on “[The Regularity of irregularity: Rethinking migration paradigms](#)”, which participants of the training school were encouraged to participate. Organised by the MirreM team at the Department for Migration and Globalisation in collaboration with key MirreM partners involved in assessing the quantitative dimension of migrant irregularity, the event brought together participants from across Europe, North Africa, the Middle East and North America to explore the quantitative dimensions of migrant irregularity.

Over the course of two and a half days, attendees engaged in hands-on workshops and expert-led lectures that covered statistical indicators, estimation methods, conceptual frameworks for measuring irregular migrant populations as well as ethical and political aspects of quantifying migrant irregularity. Sessions focused on practical tools for interpreting available data, estimating population sizes, and analysing the living and working conditions of migrants with irregular status. In addition to technical training, the programme facilitated in-depth discussions between participants involving both early career stage researchers and practitioners working at national institutions, civil society organisations and international organisations on different aspects of conceptualising, quantifying and disseminating information on irregular migration, fostering a collaborative environment for knowledge exchange. The following syllabus provides an overview of the training programme of the two and a half days. It offers a model how a short intensive training on irregular migration data – or indeed related topics – can be implemented and hopefully serves as an inspiration and useful resource for university teachers as well as trainers working with practitioners.

Further course materials (e.g. lecture slides) can be obtained upon request at info@irregularmigration.eu or from individual trainers involved in the programme.

We recommend using the *Handbook on irregular migration data. Concepts, methods and practices* (Kierans & Kraler, 2025) as key resource for a training.

Denis Kierans & Albert Kraler (eds.). *Handbook on Irregular Migration Data. Concepts, Methods and Practices*. Krems: University of Krems Press, 2025.
<https://doi.org/10.48341/g31s-vq79>

SYLLABUS

Session 1: Introduction to Basic Concepts: What is Irregular Migration? Who Belongs to the Population of Irregular Migrants? What are Stocks and Flows?	
Session Instructor(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Albert Kraler (University for Continuing Education - Danube University Krems)
Learning outcomes	<p>By the end of this session, participants will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Be familiar with different conceptualisations of migrant irregularity, their scope and various dimensions of irregularity Understand the different epistemological, disciplinary and methodological foundations of different conceptual approaches (legal vs. sociological perspectives; static vs. dynamic perspectives, etc.) Be able to apply different perspectives in analysing irregular migration
Session description	<p>This session introduces key definitions and related conceptualisations of irregular migration, in part drawing on participants' pre-participation essays.</p> <p>We will begin by clarifying fundamental legal and demographic terms (e.g. migrants, stocks, flows, foreign nationals) and identifying core analytical dimensions that shape understanding of migrant irregularity. These include national jurisdictions, individual's legal attachment to different legal orders, and distinctions between movement and residence, etc.</p> <p>Using a mapping of terminology, we will explore how different terms used to describe migrants in an irregular situation (and related populations) carry distinct connotations, geographies and underlying assumptions. This will provide a foundation for examining how different conceptualisations of migrant irregularity are constructed and how they are shaped by various epistemological and disciplinary perspectives.</p> <p>Finally, we will discuss the role of migration law in structuring legal status positions and a related hierarchy of rights, by using the lens of 'civic stratification'.</p>
Format	This session will be based on an interactive discussion, involving short instructor-led inputs, plenary discussions, and short, small group work to encourage critical engagement with key concepts.
Key reading	Kraler, A., & Ahrens, J. (2023). Conceptualising Migrant Irregularity for Measurement Purposes. In <i>MIRREM Working Paper No. 2 (Version 3)</i> . Krems: University for Continuing Education Krems (Danube University Krems). https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7868237
Suggested additional readings and resources	Ambrosini, M. (2016), From "illegality" to Tolerance and Beyond: Irregular Immigration as a Selective and Dynamic Process. <i>International Migration</i> , 54(1), 144-159 https://doi.org/10.1111/imig.12214

	<p>Chauvin, S., and Garcés-Mascareñas, B. (2012). Beyond Informal Citizenship: The New Moral Economy of Migrant Illegality. <i>International Political Sociology</i> 6(3): 241–59. https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1749-5687.2012.00162.x</p> <p>De Genova, N. P. (2002). Migrant ‘Illegality’ and Deportability in Everyday Life. <i>Annual Review of Anthropology</i> 31(1): 419–47. https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.anthro.31.040402.085432</p> <p>European Commission. Directorate General for Home Affairs and European Migration Network. (2024). <i>Asylum and Migration Glossary</i> https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/networks/european-migration-network-emn/emn-asylum-and-migration-glossary_en (online resource only)</p> <p>Hinterberger, K. F. (2023). <i>Regularisations of Irregularly Staying Migrants in the EU. A Comparative Legal Analysis of Austria, Germany and Spain</i>. Vienna: Nomos https://doi.org/10.5771/9783748912798, pp. 59-46</p> <p>Jasso, G., Massey, D. S., Rosenzweig, M. R., & Smith, J. P. (2008). From Illegal to Legal: Estimating Previous Illegal Experience among New Legal Immigrants to the United States. <i>International Migration Review</i>, 42(4), 803-843. https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1747-7379.2008.00148.x</p> <p>Sironi, A., Bauloz, C., and Emmanuel, M.. (2019). Glossary on Migration. International Organization of Migration. https://publications.iom.int/system/files/pdf/iml_34_glossary.pdf</p>
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Session 2: What is 'Good' Data? Validity, Reliability, and FAIR Data Principles in the Context of Irregular Migration Data.	
Session Instructor(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lalaine Siruno (United Nations University-MERIT/ Maastricht University) • Arjen Leerkes (Maastricht University/ Erasmus University Rotterdam)
Learning outcomes	<p>By the end of this session, participants will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the concepts of data validity (accuracy) and reliability (consistency) and their importance in migration research • Be familiar with the FAIR data principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) and how statistical agencies like Eurostat apply them • Recognise the challenges in ensuring high-quality data in the context of irregular migration, where data gaps and measurement difficulties are common
Session description	<p>This session provides foundational knowledge for the following workshop on utilising publicly available data on irregular migration.</p> <p>We will explore key considerations when assessing the quality of irregular migration data, focusing on validity and reliability. The session will introduce the FAIR data principles and examine how organisations like Eurostat apply them in practice. To ground these concepts in real-world applications, we will analyse case studies from the MIRREM and FAIR projects and other relevant research initiatives.</p>

Format	This interactive session will be a combination of a teacher-led lecture and a short small group discussion, where participants will analyse real-world data examples and reflect on the challenges of ensuring validity and reliability in irregular migration statistics.
Key readings	<p>Babbie, E. R. (2021). <i>The Practice of Social Research</i> (15th ed.). Cengage Learning Inc. [especially Chapter 5]</p> <p>Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., Blomberg, N., Boiten, J.-W., da Silva Santos, L. B., Bourne, P. E., Bouwman, J., Brookes, A. J., Clark, T., Crosas, M., Dillo, I., Dumon, O., Edmunds, S., Evelo, C. T., Finkers, R., . . . Mons, B. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship. <i>Scientific Data</i>, 3(1), 160018. https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18</p>
Suggested additional readings and resources	<p>Achermann, C. (2009). Multi-perspective research on foreigners in prisons in Switzerland. In I. van Liempt & V. Bilger (Eds.), <i>Ethics of Migration Research Methodology: Dealing with Vulnerable Immigrants</i> (pp. 42-80). Sussex Academic Press.</p> <p>Eurostat. (2021). European Statistical System (ESS) Handbook for Quality and Metadata Reports. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-manuals-and-guidelines/-/ks-gq-21-021</p> <p>Eurostat. (2024). Enforcement of immigration legislation statistics.</p> <p>Leerkes, A., Van Os, R., & Boersema, E. (2017). What drives ‘soft deportation’? Understanding the rise in Assisted Voluntary Return among rejected asylum seekers in the Netherlands. <i>Population, Space and Place</i>, 23(8), e2059. https://doi.org/10.1002/psp.2059</p> <p>Massey, D. S., & Capoferro, C. (2004). Measuring undocumented migration. <i>International Migration Review</i>, 38(3), 1075-1102. https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1747-7379.2004.tb00229.x</p> <p>Sinnige, M., Cleton, L., & Leerkes, A. (2025). Determinants of Enforced Return: A Quantitative Analysis of the Spectrum of (In) voluntariness Among Rejected Asylum Seekers in the Netherlands. <i>Population, Space and Place</i>, 31(2), e2886. https://doi.org/10.1002/psp.2886</p> <p>Staring, R. (2009). Different methods to research irregular migration. In I. van Liempt & V. Bilger (Eds.), <i>Ethics of Migration Research Methodology: Dealing with Vulnerable Immigrants</i> (pp. 83-97). Sussex Academic Press.</p> <p>Taylor, L. (2017). What is data justice? The case for connecting digital rights and freedoms globally. <i>Big Data & Society</i>, 4(2). https://doi.org/10.1177/2053951717736335</p>

Sessions 3&4: Workshop – Using Publicly Available Data on Irregular Migration to Describe Irregular Migration

Session Instructor(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Denis Kierans (University of Oxford), • Arjen Leerkes (University of Maastricht/Erasmus University Rotterdam)
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lalaine Siruno (University of Maastricht)
Learning outcomes	<p>By the end of this session, participants will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Be familiar with some of the latest research on irregular migration stocks and flows • Understand the strengths and limitations of irregular migration data • Be able to apply the MlrreM quality assessment criteria to irregular migration data • Critically assess and contextualise the use of irregular migration data in various settings.
Session description	<p>In this workshop, we will discuss the findings from the MlrreM project work in relation to estimates and indicators of irregular migration stocks and flows. We will cover the compilation and evaluation of estimates and indicators, as well as the broader findings of the research and some of its impacts. However, the bulk of the session will be dedicated to hands-on group work, focussed on participants’ learning how to interrogate the quality of irregular migration estimates and reflect these details when they use the data.</p> <p>The session will begin with presentations by the instructors, covering:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MlrreM quality assessment criteria for irregular migration stocks and flows • Demonstrate how to assess irregular migration data, using specific country-level examples • Cross-country insights into the quality of irregular migration data and trends across countries. • Broader impacts and policy implications of the research <p>Following the presentation, the participants will then be divided into smaller groups, to apply the MlrreM quality criteria to asses irregular migration data. The composition of the groups will be pre-determined by the instructors, to ensure diversity in background/training and current roles/affiliations. Using the pre-participation essay (country context document), or other relevant resource, the groups will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analyse the quality of selected irregular migration dataset. • Develop a narrative that accounts for the irregular migration data strengths, limitations and biases. • Guiding questions will prompt participants to reflect on how these data are used in policymaking, media reporting, and otherwise circulate in public discourse. • Participants will also be prompted to reflect on their use of irregular migration data in their own work and exchange insights and practice. <p>Each group will present their findings in the plenary, highlighting key takeaways. The session will conclude with a synthesis of insights, including an inventory of good practices and potential pitfalls when using publicly available data on irregular migration.</p>
Format	<p>This session will follow an interactive workshop format, consisting of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A short introductory presentation by the instructors • Group work with structured analysis and discussion, • Group presentations in a plenary session, • A wrap-up discussion to consolidate key findings.
Key readings	<p>Kierans, D., & Vargas-Silva, C. (2024) The Irregular Migrant Population of Europe. MlrreM Working Paper No. 11 (Version 1). Krems: University for Continuing</p>

	<p>Education Krems (Danube University Krems). https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13857073</p> <p>Siruno, L., Leerkes, A., Hendow, M., & Brunovská, E. (2024) MirreM Working Paper on Irregular Migration Flows. In MirreM Working Paper No. 9. Krems: University for Continuing Education Krems (Danube University Krems). https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10702228</p>
<p>Suggested additional readings and resources</p>	<p>Boswell, C. (2009). Knowledge, Legitimation and the Politics of Risk: The Functions of Research in Public Debates on Migration, <i>Political Studies</i>, 57(1), 165-186. https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9248.2008.00729.x</p> <p>Vespe, M., Natale, C. and Pappalardo, L. (2017). Data sets on irregular migration and irregular migrants in the European Union, <i>Migration Policy Practice</i>, 7(2), 29-33. https://publications.iom.int/system/files/pdf/migration_policy_practice_journal_30.pdf</p> <p>Vollmer, B. A. (2011). Policy Discourses on Irregular Migration in the EU-‘Number Games’ and ‘Political Games’. <i>European Journal of Migration and Law</i>, 13(3), 317-339. https://doi.org/10.1163/157181611X587874</p> <p>Savatic, F., Thiollet, H., Mesnard, A., Senne, J.-N., & Jaulin, T. (2024). Borders Start with Numbers: How Migration Data Create ‘Fake Illegals’. <i>International Migration Review</i>, 1-32. https://doi.org/10.1177/01979183231222169</p> <p><u>Media coverage (sample):</u></p> <p>Dampier, G. (2025) “Enough learnt helplessness. Here’s how Britain ends illegal migration” in The Telegraph, 24 January 2025. https://www.telegraph.co.uk/news/2025/01/24/enough-learned-helplessness-britain-end-illegal-migration/</p> <p>Hymas, C. (2024) “Britain has most illegal migrants in Europe, study finds” in The Telegraph, 7 October 2024. https://www.telegraph.co.uk/politics/2024/10/07/britain-has-most-illegal-migrants-in-europe-study-finds/</p> <p>Tahir, T. (2024) “Evidence shows far-right claims on illegal migrants are 'hyperbolic'” in The National, 7 October 2024. https://www.thenationalnews.com/news/europe/2024/10/07/static-illegal-migrant-numbers-undermine-hyperbolic-far-right-campaigns-in-europe/</p> <p>Taylor, D. (2024) “Irregular migration into UK and large European countries is same as 2008, research shows” in The Guardian, 7 October 2024.</p>

<p>Sessions 5: Methods for Estimating Irregular Migration</p>	
<p>Session Instructor(s)</p>	<p>Alejandra Rodríguez Sánchez (University of Potsdam)</p>
<p>Learning outcomes</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gain insight into the primary traditional methods employed for estimating irregular migration.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Critically evaluate the limitations and challenges associated with these conventional approaches. • Comprehend the objectives and advancements offered by innovative estimation techniques. • Acquire hands-on experience with traditional estimation methods through the application of simulated data.
<p>Session description</p>	<p>This workshop introduces participants to methodologies used in estimating irregular migration, highlighting their assumptions, limitations, and potential biases. The session begins with an overview of why estimating irregular migration is crucial, considering its dual-use problem (research and policy) and ethical dimensions. It then covers common estimation methods, including survey-based approaches, demographic models, and statistical techniques such as multiple systems estimation and residual methods.</p> <p>Using real-world case studies, including the PEW Research Center's approach and examples from Japan, the U.S., and Australia, participants will explore the application of these methods across different contexts.</p> <p>In the second part of the session, participants will engage in a practical exercise using simulated data. Working in groups, they will attempt to replicate one of the discussed methods using R, allowing them to apply theoretical concepts in practice. The session concludes with a discussion on innovative approaches, including alternative data sources such as rice consumption, flight data, and biometric records, as well as potential methodological advancements in irregular migration estimation.</p> <p>Session Structure:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Introduction: Why is estimating irregular migration important? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. The dual-use problem (research and policymaking) b. Ethical considerations 2. Common methods for estimating irregular migration stocks and flows <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Survey-based approaches b. Demographic methods c. Multiple systems estimation d. Residual methods 3. Case Studies <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. PEW Research Center's approach in different countries b. Estimation examples from Japan, the U.S., and Australia 4. Practical Exercise: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Using simulated data to replicate one of the estimation methods in R 5. Innovative Approaches to Estimating Irregular Migration <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Improving traditional methods b. Exploring new data sources: Rice consumption, flight data, biometric data (Example: SAR data for border monitoring) c. Developing new methodological approaches 6. Conclusion & Key Takeaways <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Summary of key methods and their limitations b. Reflection on ethical considerations and data gaps c. Future directions in irregular migration research

Format	<p>This session will follow the following format:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short lecture introducing key concepts and methodologies • Case study discussions • Hands-on data exercise in R • Group work and discussion
Key readings	<p>Rodríguez Sánchez, A., & Tjaden, J. (2023). <i>Estimating Irregular Migration – A Review of Traditional and Innovative Methods</i>. MIRreM Working Paper No. 4 (Version 2). Krems: University for Continuing Education Krems (Danube University Krems). https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8380854</p>
Suggested additional readings and resources	<p>Jandl, M. (2011). Methods, approaches and data sources for estimating stocks of irregular migrants. <i>International Migration</i>, 49(5), 53-77. https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2435.2011.00701.x</p> <p>Van Hook, J., Morse, A., Capps, R., & Gelatt, J. (2021). <i>Uncertainty about the Size of the Unauthorized Foreign-Born Population in the United States</i>. <i>Demography</i>, 58(6), 2315-2336. https://doi.org/10.1215/00703370-9491801</p> <p>Nixon, S. (2022). Of Rice and Men: Rice Consumption-Based Estimates of Undocumented Persons in Malaysia. <i>International Migration Review</i>, 019791832211264. https://doi.org/10.1177/01979183221126466</p> <p>Taylor, D. (2024) “Irregular migration into UK and large European countries is same as 2008, research shows” in <i>The Guardian</i>, 7 October 2024.</p>

Session 6: Policy impacts on irregular migration and the lives of irregular migrants	
Session Instructor(s)	Alejandra Rodríguez Sánchez (University of Potsdam)
Learning outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Critically evaluate the framing of policy claims related to irregular migration as presented in the literature • Identify and explain the challenges in identifying and estimating policy effects • Explain different methodological approaches used to assess policy impacts
Session description	<p>Migration policy is currently one of the most salient issues in political debates and the media. Yet their impact is difficult to assess. In this workshop, students will learn the basic framework for the evaluation of policies aimed at controlling or reducing migration, with a special focus on irregular migration. We will discuss the different type of policies (or policy messages) often enacted with the purpose of changing the incentives of migrants. We will look at the methods used in the literature to estimate these effects, the data available, and the pitfalls or challenges of empirical studies. We will engage in a hypothetical study aimed at identifying the impact of a change in policy in the probability of overstaying. The study of policy impacts on irregular migration is riddled with substantial challenges.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Types of policies 2. Features of policies <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Sequential b. Random (variation in time or space)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> c. Differences across countries d. Micro and Macro studies <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Causal Inference for evaluating policy impacts <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Challenges for micro studies (selection bias) b. Challenges for macro studies 4. Case studies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. US-Mexico b. Australia c. Central Mediterranean 5. Exercise: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Hypothetical evaluation: What are the effects of policies A, B, and C on overstaying your visa? 6. Conclusions
Format	This session will be based on an interactive discussion, involving short inputs by the session instructor, plenary discussions, and short group work
Key reading	Rodríguez Sánchez, A., Wucherpennig, J., Rischke, R., & Iacus, S. M. (2023). Search-and-rescue in the Central Mediterranean Route does not induce migration: Predictive modeling to answer causal queries in migration research. <i>Scientific Reports</i> , 13(1), 11014. https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-38119-4
Suggested additional readings and resources	<p>Czaika, M., & De Haas, H. (2016). <i>The Effect of Visas on Migration Processes</i>. <i>International Migration Review</i>, 50(3), 626-657. https://heindehaas.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/the-effect-of-visas-on-migration-on-migration-processes-2017.pdf</p> <p>Massey, D. S., & Pren, K. A. (2012). Unintended consequences of US immigration policy: Explaining the post-1965 surge from Latin America. <i>Population and development review</i>, 38(1), 1-29. https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1728-4457.2012.00470.x</p> <p>McKenzie, D., & Yang, D. (2024). Field and natural experiments in migration. In <i>Handbook of Research Methods in Migration</i> (pp. 48-82). Edward Elgar Publishing. https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/bd17d3b9-8d7c-5340-99b4-bc1d2b88875b/content</p>

Session 7: The Politics and Ethics of Numbers	
Session Instructor(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Arjen Leerkes (Maastricht University/Erasmus University Rotterdam) • Albert Kraler (University for Continuing Education - Danube University Krems)
Learning outcomes	<p>By the end of this session participants will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Critically assess ethical challenges in irregular migration research • Analyse the political dynamics influencing migration research • Interrogate the impact of migration statistics on policy and public discourse • Develop strategies for ethical research design and dissemination

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhance responsible engagement with policy and public debates
Session description	<p>This session explores the ethical and political challenges of researching irregular migration, emphasising the risks of misuse and politicisation of research findings. Drawing on ethical guidelines from the European Sociological Association and Dutch universities, the session will address concerns around research integrity, informed consent, and mitigating vulnerabilities.</p> <p>Using insights from Horizon Europe projects on return policies and irregular migration measurement, participants will examine the ethical dilemmas researchers face, including the balance between academic freedom and policy engagement. The session will also apply Burawoy’s (2005) typology of sociology—professional, policy, public, and critical—to demonstrate the legitimate role of social science in migration research.</p> <p>A key focus will be on strategies to navigate ethical dilemmas, including fostering ongoing ethical reflection, ensuring balanced research design, engaging diverse stakeholders, and promoting transparency. The session will critically reflect on the risks of publication bias and the responsibilities of researchers when their work enters public and policy debates.</p>
Format	<p>The session will consist of a mix of a lecture type and interactive formats. A brief double lecture on the different roles of scientific research in policy making and ethical challenges arising from these different roles will introduce and frame the session. In the second part of the session, we invite participants to reflect on ethical challenges encountered in research they have or are conducting and their ways to address these.</p>
Key reading	<p>Cyrus, N. (2023). Ethical Benchmarking for the Measurement of Irregular Migration. In <i>MIRreM Policy Brief No.1</i>. Krems: University for Continuing Education Krems (Danube University Krems). https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042022</p>
Suggested additional readings and resources	<p>Burawoy, M. (2005). For public sociology. <i>American sociological review</i>, 70(1), 4-28. https://doi.org/10.1177/000312240507000102</p> <p>Bauböck, R., Mourão Permoser, J., & Ruhs, M. (2022). The ethics of migration policy dilemmas. <i>Migration Studies</i>, 10(3), 427-441. https://doi.org/10.1093/migration/mnac029</p> <p>Cyrus, N. (2023). Ethical Benchmarking in Irregular Migration Research. In <i>MIRreM Working Paper No.3</i>. Krems: University for Continuing Education Krems (Danube University Krems). https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8389189</p> <p>Düvell, F., Triandafyllidou, A., & Vollmer, B. (2010). Ethical issues in irregular migration research in Europe. <i>Population, Space and Place</i>, 16(3), 227-239. https://doi.org/10.1002/psp.590</p> <p>van Liempt, I., Bilger, V. (2018). Methodological and Ethical Dilemmas in Research Among Smuggled Migrants. In: Zapata-Barrero, R., Yalaz, E. (eds) <i>Qualitative Research in European Migration Studies</i>. IMISCOE Research Series. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-76861-8_15</p>